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Passive cooling based battery thermal management using phase change materials for electric vehicles

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Summary

Lithium-ion capacitors (LiC) are considered as one of the major options for high power applications due to their high power capability. However, thermal runaway associated with the LiC systems in automotive applications due to high-current solicitation can significantly result in a considerable reduction in the vehicles' performance and life cycle. The purpose of a thermal management system (TMS) is to maintain the energy storage system at an optimum target temperature following by performance and life cycle tradeoff. This paper aims at proposing a passive TMS using phase change materials (PCM). In this regard, the passive TMS is designed, and the performance of the system is analyzed and validated, utilizing Simcenter AMESim[®] and the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software, COMSOL Multiphysics[®].

Keywords: thermal management system (TMS), phase change material (PCM), computational fluid dynamics (CFD), Lithium-ion capacitor (LiC), thermal circuit.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, by increasing the number of vehicles and rising fuel consumption, there would be a question of the tolerability of environmental pollution. The possible solution has been the investigation of zero-emission vehicles to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Plug-in hybrid vehicles and battery electric vehicles are amongst the best candidates for rechargeable energy storage systems due to lithium-ion batteries (LiB) utilized for traction [1]. However, it seems the proposed solution has its drawbacks like escalated aging phenomena, which limits the lifetime of the system [2]. One of the solutions to this problem has been the usage of a hybrid structure utilizing li-ion batteries and supercapacitors (SC), which results in the emergence of lithium-ion

capacitors (LiC). LiC is a hybrid rechargeable energy storage system (RESS) that combines the advantages of LiBs with SCs such as extended temperature window compared to SCs, high power density, and longer lifetime in comparison with LiBs [3]. Nevertheless, LiCs show limited performance when exposed to high heat generation due to high current applications [4]. Therefore, there is a crucial need for designing a proper thermal management system (TMS) to avoid non-uniform temperature evolution, and in the worst scenario, thermal runaway.

Many research studies have been conducted to develop a proper thermal management system, including passive and active cooling methods. Air-cooling and liquid-cooling are the typical active cooling systems for thermal management of energy storage and electronic cooling devices [5]. Air-cooling is the most used TMS due to its simple structure and low cost, but its efficiency is rather low compared with liquid cooling systems for high power applications [6]. However, forced air-cooling requires energy consumption for the airflow, and it is considered as an active method, which comes with extra cost during production, operation, and maintenance. It usually employs air or a liquid as coolant. In contrast, the cooling capacity of liquid cooling systems is more than air cooling systems, but possible leakage inside the module is the most common drawback of these systems. Moreover, liquid cooling systems are massive and costly to install, and their maintenance cost is rather high [7].

On the other hand, passive cooling methods such as phase-change materials (PCM) consume no energy or need low energy to operate in cooling and thermal energy storage applications [8–10]. Lately, hybrid TMS with passive and active cooling is being under research. Regarding this, PCMs are quite attractive candidates due to their high energy storage capability, reduced volume, low complexity, and expense, compared to the aforementioned active TMS [11]. A thorough review of studies that incorporate PCMs for automotive applications can be found in our previous work [12].

The most crucial part of designing a proper TMS is the development of the thermal model to understand battery behavior. To the author's knowledge, the lack of a thermal management system for LiCs can be seen in the literature. Soltani et al. [13] developed a detailed thermal model utilizing an air cooling system for the LiC module. Jaguemont et al., in our latest work [14], developed a passive thermal management system utilizing a phase change material (PCM) to cool down a dual-LiC system.

Therefore, in this work, the detailed 3-D thermal model of the LiC system is developed using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software, COMSOL Multiphysics. Moreover, in addition to the successive 3-D thermal model, the 1-D model of the thermal circuit will be proposed by using Simcenter Amesim, to validate the experimental results. The goal of the model is to provide accurate thermal results without the complexity of the 3-D modeling equation. This way, the model can be used for a future optimization algorithm activity. The rest of this paper is structured as follows: In section 2, the experimental setup is presented, and the results are

depicted. Then, Numerical analysis and 1-D and 3-D thermal models are described in section 3. Section 4 deals with the results and optimization of the module. Finally, conclusions are given in section 5.

2 Experimental setup

The proposed passive thermal management system used in this work consists of two LiC cells to represent a module structure to be used in an EV. To this end, the commercial 2300 F prismatic lithium-ion capacitor is utilized, which is demonstrated in Fig. 1-a. The specifications of this cell are given in Table 1. The experimental setup consists of two LiC cells, a casing, paraffin PCM, and aluminum foil. Fig. 1-b demonstrates the developed thermal management system (TMS), which is capable of capturing the generated heat of the LiC module with PCM-Al-foil structure. The module is put inside a climate chamber to fix its temperature, in which the temperature is set to 25 °C. A Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) case holds the cells which can contain the PCM inside. As the thermal conductivity of the paraffin PCM is low (around 0.2 W/m.K), the heat generated during the cycling process can not fully be absorbed by the PCM. Hence, a high conductive heat transfer material like Aluminum mesh grid foil (Al-foil) is added to the system to enhance the thermal conductivity of the TMS.

Figure 1: a) The LiC cell, b) The proposed passive TMS inside the climate chamber

Table 1: Specifications of the LiC cell

Parameters	Value	Unit
Capacitance	2300	F
Nominal cell voltage	3.3	V
Cell weight	0.3	Kg
Current rate	1-1000	A

The first step of this work is dedicated to evaluate the temperature of the module without using any TMS. Hence, the module is put inside the chamber without adding PCM inside the casing. The next step is to pour the PCM to investigate the effect of PCM TMS on the temperature evolution of the module. The case study

consists of 13 mm PCM, which has been poured inside the casing. The used PCM is depicted in Fig. 2, which its properties are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The Paraffin PCM features used for the passive TMS

Parameters	Value	Unit
Melting area	32-44	°C
Freezing area	23-30	°C
Latent heat of fusion	236	kJ/kg
Specific heat in solid phase	2500	J/(kg.K)
Specific heat in liquid phase	2800	J/(kg.K)
Thermal conductivity	0.2	(W/(m.K))

Figure 2: The phase change material (PCM) used in the passive TMS

The PCM is in the solid phase when it is exposed to environment temperature. Hence, it should be placed in a climate chamber to change its phase to liquid. After all the PCM becomes liquid, it should be poured into the casing. The thermal conductivity of the casing is 0.19 W.m.K, and the material of the casing is polyvinyl chloride (PVC). The selected casing has enough strength to keep the PCM inside when the PCM is changing its phase from solid to liquid when absorbs heat from the module. As it is mentioned in the literature, the low thermal conductivity of PCMs limits their ability to absorb heat from the batteries. In this work, aluminum mesh grid foil (Al-foil) is added to the paraffin PCM to enhance its thermal conductivity. To this end, Al-foil is wrapped around the dual-cells very tight.

Fig. 3 depicts the experimental facilities of the MOBI laboratory located in the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), which is used to carry out precise experimental tests. The MOBI test bench comprises a climate chamber, battery tester, data collector, and a linked computer. Also, infrared (IR) thermal camera with a 2% error is used to capture thermal pictures. The battery tester is used to gather the data from the cycling of the LiC module. The current, voltage, and temperature of the module will be monitored, the definition of the test will be

handled, and the current rate value will be evaluated. The module is cycled by 150 A current rate during the 1300 s current profile to perform the charge/discharge process. After putting the module inside the climate chamber (25 °C fixed temperature), and attaching the voltage and current cables, the average heat generation of 18 W is measured during the discharge process.

Figure 3: The climate chamber with battery tester and data collector

3 Numerical analysis

The first step in designing a competent TMS is to develop the thermal model to have a thorough understanding of battery behavior. Hence, Based on the experimental methodology, a 1-D/3-D thermal model is developed in this work, which is validated against experimental results. This comprehensive 1D-3D model is capable of capturing the temperature distribution of the LiC module. The main aim is to design a compact and light-weight TMS to be efficient enough utilized in an electric vehicle (EV).

3.1 1-D model development

1-D thermal model of the PCM can propose a more cost-effective solution to absorb the generated heat, which its benefits depend on the system. In this regard, the PCM structure was considered to be integrated into the thermal circuit of the dual-cell LiC module. The generated heat is being absorbed by the PCM through the thermal mass of the module. The characteristics of the used PCM are the same as an experiment and 3-D CFD thermal model. Fig. 4 presents the PCM model as a part of the thermal circuit in the Simcenter Amesim simulation tool. This model is still under development.

Figure 4: Simcenter Amesim model of the LiC-Dual-cell module with PCM

The energy density equation for the latent thermal energy storage (PCM) can be described by:

$$q_{latent} \left(\frac{kJ}{kg} \right) = \frac{Q}{m} = C_p \Delta T + h_f \quad (1)$$

Where Q , m , and C_p are the generated heat, mass, and the specific heat capacity. ΔT is the total temperature change of the system, and h_f is the latent heat of fusion of the PCM. This analysis assumes that the energy can be extracted from the PCM, which depends on the heat transfer characteristics of the PCM. 1-D thermal circuit analysis presumes that energy is readily absorbed by the PCM, which depends on the heat transfer characteristics of the PCM. In this regard, AMESim as the simulation environment is used for the thermal performance analysis, since it has specific libraries for thermal system models.

3.2 3-D model development

Fig. 5 shows the 3-D model of the proposed TMS designed in Autodesk Inventor software, comprising a dual-cell prismatic LiC, PCM, and the PVC casing. This model will be imported in COMSOL to investigate the temperature evolution of the module by using heat transfer in solids (ht) COMSOL module. With the designed system, the generated heat is being absorbed by the PCM-Al thanks to the high thermal conductivity of the PCM-Al structure.

Figure 5: The CAD geometry of the proposed TMS

3.3 Mesh grid independence analysis

Mesh generation of the system should be performed after designing the TMS. To do so, the tetrahedral mesh is selected. The mesh selection and solver have a significant impact on the accuracy of the results and the speed of calculation. Also, mesh independence analysis is used to save time and memory usage, as well as to increase the simulation precision. The maximum module temperature is used for grid independency analysis, which can be seen in Fig. 6. According to this figure, from 43K mesh elements to 145K mesh elements, the results remain almost the same. Hence, 43K mesh elements have been chosen for the simulation process to get precise results, while the calculation time is being saved.

Figure 6: Grid independence analysis (left), and generated mesh of the module (right)

4 Results and discussion

In this section, the experimental results are validated against 1-D/3-D simulation studies for the TMS defined earlier. The temperature evolution of the module is captured using the IR thermal camera, and a comparison is carried out between simulation studies and experimental test results to validate the precision of the numerical methodology for three cases: the module without TMS, pure paraffin PCM, and PCM-Al structure.

4.1 Temperature evolution of the module without using TMS

The tested system for the first case study is without any cooling system to get the thermal behavior of the system. From the temperature evolution of the LiC module, one can conclude that the maximum temperature exceeds the safety limit. At this temperature, the degradation of the cells occurs, which proves the need for an efficient TMS.

Figure 7: Graphical comparison of the module without TMS

Fig. 7 illustrates a perfect match between simulation results of the 1-D thermal circuit, 3-D CFD analysis, and experimental results.

4.2 Pure paraffin PCM TMS

In this step, the paraffin PCM is poured into the PVC casing to absorb the generated heat of the module during cycling. By using this TMS, the temperature decreases since the PCM can store the thermal load inside itself thanks to its latent heat. Fig. 8 presents good accordance between 1-D/3-D simulations and IR thermal image curve. The temperature difference between the system with TMS and without TMS is 3.5 °C (45.5 °C for without TMS and 42 °C for PCM TMS). Nevertheless, the maximum module temperature with pure paraffin PCM is still high, so the thermal conductivity of the PCM has to be increased to remove the absorbed energy.

Figure 8: Graphical comparison of the pure paraffin PCM TMS

4.3 PCM-Al structure

After adding Al-foil to the PCM to enhance the main drawback of PCMs, the thermal conductivity increases sharply, which results in rejecting the absorbed heat to the environment. The dual-cell LiC module was surrounded by the aluminum mesh grid foil, which rejects the generated heat faster thanks to its enhanced thermal conductivity. As Fig. 9 shows, PCM-Al reduces the surface temperature of the module and also improves uniformity. The maximum module temperature is around 36 °C, which is better than pure PCM solution. Nevertheless, the added Al-foil increases the cost of the system as well as the weight of the system, which is not favorable for industrial applications, such as in the automotive industry. Hence, performance indicators should be optimized to be used in real applications.

Figure 9: Graphical comparison of the PCM-Al structure

4.4 Comparative study

In this section, the comparison of the experimental, 1-D simulation, and 3-D simulation results are given to investigate the performance of the designed thermal model. The results show that the LiC module can work stably under practical operating conditions for the long term. The thermal analysis within 1-D/3-D thermal modeling was regarded as a fundamental step to reach a more optimal balance between the performance of the TMS and the cost of the system. Fig. 10 represents the comparative study to evaluate the performance of the system. A perfect match between experiment results, the 1-D thermal circuit simulation, and the 3-D CFD thermal model simulation is observed. Also, Adding Al-foil to the PCM successfully decreases the temperature in the module. The 1-D/3-D thermal model presented in this study is a useful modeling approach to evaluate the effect of different parameters on the thermal behavior of the LiC module in an electric vehicle battery module under driving cycles. Also, the results can be used along with an aging model to study the effects of thermal management systems on the long term performance of battery modules after repeated driving cycles.

Figure 10: Comparative study between no-TMS strategy, pure PCM, and PCM-Al structure

5 Conclusion

In this work, a new thermal management system (TMS) was proposed, which consists of a phase change material (PCM) surrounded by aluminum mesh grid foil (Al-foil) to increase the thermal conductivity of a LiC dual-cell module. Three different scenarios were investigated, such as the system without TMS, pure PCM, and PCM-Al. The maximum module temperature was achieved during the discharge process, which was verified against 1-D simulation studies using AMESim software, and 3-D computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software called COMSOL. The main task was to keep the maximum module temperature within the safe operating temperature announced by the manufacturer.

The experimental results are validated against 1-D/3-D thermal simulations. Results showed that in comparison with the system without TMS, paraffin PCM is able to improve the temperature evolution of the module by 4.1 °C. After adding the Al-foil to the PCM, the lower temperature was achieved (PCM: 41.6 °C, PCM-Al: 36.2 °C), while the uniformity of the module was enhanced.

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